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**Solving Problems by Using a Function
in The Number Theory**

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SOLVING PROBLEMS BY USING A FUNCTION IN THE NUMBER THEORY

Let $n \geq 1, h \geq 1,$ and $a \geq 2$ be integers. For which values of a and n is $(n+h)!$ a multiple of a^n ? (A generalization of the problem $n^0 = 1270$, *Mathematics Magazine*, Vol. 60, No. 3, June 1987, p. 179, proposed by Roger B. Eggleton, The University of Newcastle, Australia.)

Solution (For $h = 1$ the problem $n^0 = 1270$ is obtained.)

§1. Introduction

We have constructed a function η (see [1]) having the following properties:

- (a) For each non-null integer $n, \eta(n)!$ is multiple of n ;
- (b) $\eta(n)$ is the smallest natural number with the property (a).

It is easy to prove:

Lemma 1. $(\forall) k, p \in N^*, p \neq 1, k$ is uniquely written in the form:

$$k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)},$$

where $a_{n_i}^{(p)} = (p^{n_i} - 1)/(p - 1), i = 1, 2, \dots, l, n_1 > n_2 > \dots > n_l > 0$ and $1 \leq t_j \leq (p - 1), j = 1, 2, \dots, l - 1, 1 \leq t_l \leq p, n_j, t_j \in N, i = 1, 2, \dots, l, l \in N^*$.

We have constructed the function η_p, p prime $> 0, \eta_p: N^* \rightarrow N^*$, thus :

$$(\forall) n \in N^*, \eta_p(a_n^{(p)}) = p^n, \text{ and } \eta_p(t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)}) = t_1 \eta_p(a_{n_1}^{(p)}) + \dots + t_l \eta_p(a_{n_l}^{(p)}).$$

Of course:

Lemma 2. (a) $(\forall) k \in N^*, \eta_p(k)! = Mp^k$.

(b) $\eta_p(k)$ is the smallest number with the property (a). Now, we construct another function:

$\eta : Z \setminus 0 \rightarrow N$ defined is follows:

$$\begin{cases} \eta(\pm 1) = 0, \\ (\forall) n = \epsilon p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s} \text{ with } \epsilon = \pm 1, p_i \text{ prime and } p_i \neq p_j \text{ for } i \neq j, \text{ all} \\ \alpha_i \in N^*, \eta(n) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq s} \{ \eta_p(\alpha_i) \} \end{cases}$$

It is not difficult to prove η has the demanded properties of §1.

§2. Now, let $a = p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}$, with all $\alpha_i \in N^*$ and all p_i distinct primes. By the previous theory we have:

$$\eta(a) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq s} \{ \eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i) \} = \eta_p(a) \text{ (by notation).}$$

$$\text{Hance } \eta(a) = \eta(p^{\alpha}), \eta(p^{\alpha})! = Mp^{\alpha}.$$

We know:

$$(t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l})! = Mp \frac{p^{n_1} - 1}{p - 1} + \dots + t_l \frac{p^{n_l} - 1}{p - 1}$$

We put:

$$t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} = n + h \text{ and } t_1 \frac{p^{n_1} - 1}{p - 1} + \dots + t_l \frac{p^{n_l} - 1}{p - 1} = \alpha n.$$

Whence

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\frac{p^{n_1} - 1}{p - 1} + \dots + t_l \frac{p^{n_l} - 1}{p - 1} \right] \geq t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - h \text{ or}$$

$$(1) \alpha(p - 1)h \geq (\alpha p - \alpha - 1)[t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l}] + (t_1 + \dots + t_l).$$

On this condition we take $n_0 = t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - h$ (see Lemma 1), hence $n = \begin{cases} n_0, n_0 > 0; \\ 1, n_0 \leq 0 \end{cases}$

Consider giving $a \neq 2$, we have a finite number of n . There is an infinite number of n if and only if $\alpha p - \alpha - 1 = 0$ i.e., $\alpha = 1$ and $p = 2$, i.e., $a = 2$

§3 Particular Case

If $h = 1$ and $a \neq 2$, because $t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} \geq p^{n_1} > 1$

and $t_1 + \dots + t_l \geq 1$, it follows from (1) that :

$$(1') (\alpha p - \alpha) > (\alpha p - \alpha - 1) \cdot 1 + 1 = \alpha p - \alpha,$$

which is impossible. If $h = 1$ and $a = 2$ then $\alpha = 1, p = 2$, or

$$(1'') 1 \leq t_1 + \dots + t_l,$$

hence $l = 1, t_1 = 1$ whence $n = t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - h = 2^{n_1} - 1, n_1 \in \mathbb{N}^*$ (the solution to problem 1270).

Example 1. Let $h = 16$ and $a = 3^4 \cdot 5^2$. Find all n such that

$$(n + 16)! = M2025^n.$$

Solution

$$\eta(2025) = \max\{\eta_3(4), \eta_5(2)\} = \max\{9, 10\} = 10 = \eta_5(2) = \eta(5^2). \text{ Whence } \alpha = 2, p = 5.$$

From (1) we have:

$$128 \geq 7[t_1 5^{n_1} + \dots + t_l 5^{n_l}] + t_1 + \dots + t_l.$$

Because $5^4 > 128$ and $7[t_1 5^{n_1} + \dots + t_l 5^{n_l}] < 128$ we find $l = 1$,

$$128 \geq 7t_1 5^{n_1} + t_1,$$

whence $n_1 \leq 1$, i.e. $n_1 = 1$, and $t_1 = 1, 2, 3$. Then $n_0 = t_1 5 - 16 < 0$, hence we take $n = 1$.

Example 2. $(n + 7)! = M3^n$ when $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$.

$(n + 7)! = M5^n$ when $n = 1$.

$(n + 7)! = M7^n$ when $n = 1$.

But $(n + 7)! \neq Mp^n$ for p prime > 7 , $(\forall)n \in N^*$.

$(n + 7)! \neq M2^n$ when

$$n_0 = t_1 2^{n_1} + \dots + t_i 2^{n_i} - 7,$$

$$t_1, \dots, t_{i-1} = 1,$$

$$1 \leq t_i \leq 2, t_1 + \dots + t_i \leq 7$$

and $n = \begin{cases} n_0, n_0 > 0; \\ 1, n_0 \leq 0. \end{cases}$ etc.

Exercise for Readers

If $n \in N^*$, $a \in N^* \setminus \{1\}$, find all values of a and n such that:

$(n + 7)!$ is a multiple of a^n .

Some Unsolved Problems (see [2])

Solve the diophantine equations:

(1) $\eta(x) \cdot \eta(y) = \eta(x + y)$.

(2) $\eta(x) = y!$ (A solution: $x = 9, y = 3$).

(3) Conjecture: the equation $\eta(x) = \eta(x + 1)$ has no solution.

References

[1] Florentine Smarandache, "A Function in the Number Theory", *Analele Univ. Timisoara*, Fasc. 1, Vol. XVIII, pp. 79-88, 1980, MR: 83c: 10008.

[2] Idem, Un Infinity of Unsolved Problems Concerning a Function in Number Theory, International Congress of Mathematicians, Univ. of Berkeley, CA, August 3-11, 1986.

[A comment about this generalization was published in "Mathematics Magazine", Vol. 61, No. 3, June 1988, p. 202: "Smarandache considered the general problem of finding positive integers n, a and k , so that $(n + k)!$ should be a multiple of a^n . Also, for positive integers p and k , with p prime, he found a formula for determining the smallest integer $f(k)$ with the property that $(f(k))!$ is a multiple of p^k ."]]